

INFLUENCE OF STRESS, EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND RELIGIOSITY ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF MARRIED COUPLES IN MAKURDI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The greater psychological well-being is contributed and enabled by an important factor known as emotional intelligence has been studied in many populations such as secondary school students, athletes, University students and elderly. However, the role of emotional intelligence, stress and religiosity in influencing psychological well-being was limited to other areas of study by previous researchers. This study was an investigation influence of emotional intelligence, stress and religiosity on psychological well-being of couples in Makurdi Local Government of Benue State. The aim of the study was to determine if stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity independently and jointly influence psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council of Benue State. A total of 350 participants were sampled using purposive sampling technique from married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. Instruments used for data collection were Stress Subscale of Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS), The Swinburne University Emotional Intelligence Test, Religious Orientation Scale, and BBC Well-being scale (BBC-WB). Data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regressions on SPSS version 26. Results indicated that stress significantly influenced psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council $R = .112$, $R^2 = .013$, $[F(1,329) = 4.168, P < .05]$. Similarly, emotional intelligence had significant influence on psychological wellbeing among married couples $R = .973$, $R^2 = .946$, $[F(5,321) = 1111.736, P < .01]$. Further analysis revealed that religiosity had significant influence on psychological wellbeing $R = .151$, $R^2 = .023$, $[F(2,345) = 3.989, P < .01]$ among participants. Additionally, stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity had significantly and jointly influenced psychological wellbeing among study participants $R = .915$, $R^2 = .937$, $[F(3,321) = 542.750, P < .01]$. Based on the study findings, it was recommended that interventions aiming to reduce stress levels, and utilising religiosity can be offered to the married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council to enhance their psychological wellbeing.

Introduction

A healthy society can be formed by couples with good and healthy relationships. Kindness and mutual trust are considered as important foundations of this kind of healthy relationship (Amiri-Majd, 2014). When a spouse does not value the relationship as much as the other one does or when the essential needs of a spouse are ignored, marital satisfaction or intimacy will be diminished also or the reason for living together will be disappeared. Intimacy is a process, in which individuals try to approach each other and discover their similarities and differences in emotions, thoughts, and behaviors (Akins & Brown, 2010).

The links between marriage and its impact on the mental, emotional and behaviour outcomes in married couples in recent times has generated much interest in Social Sciences. It appears that the quality of marital interactions and the behaviors in which couples perform their roles and their expectations with each other is linked to their psychological well-being (Balderrama & Snyder, 2013).

Although marriage offer likelihoods of psychological benefits by offering meaning and purpose, facilitating closeness between spouses, sharing financial resources, and generating emotional and moral support as previous research have established (Musick & Bumpass, 2012; Carr et al 2014), however the influence of stress, emotional intelligence, religiosity on the psychological well-being remains not fully explored, even though a large range of clinical symptoms of poor psychological wellbeing and clusters of such symptoms have been proposed as consequences of decreased psychological wellbeing among couples. Some of these consequences include; depression, hopelessness, apathy, anxiety, psychosomatic symptoms, low self-esteem, low life satisfaction, negative mood, alcoholism, and (para) suicide. There are mutual factors that contribute to couple's psychological well-being which will help in our observation; these are the quality of marital relations and the roles and expectations of the couples. Both of these factors impact on spouses' psychological well-being, as well as influence their cognitive and emotional processes, and behavior (Vanassche, et al., 2013; Segrin & Flora, 2014). The first factor of marital relations can be examined in terms of quality of marital relations which is defined as an international assessment of the marriage from several dimensions, that is looking at the positive and negative sides of couples relations such as support and strain, fight and reconciliation, as well as attitudes, and relating of behaviors and interaction patterns (Robles, et al, 2014). This understanding of marital relations emphasizes partners' subjective satisfaction with their relationships and focuses on the attitudes and behavior which determine the overall quality of marriage. This is because quality of mutual relations can also determine the durability or breakup of a marriage.

The second factor concerning roles and expectations of couples can be examined in terms of developed sets of ideas about roles and expectations that we as individuals, groups, communities, and societies in general, have demand men and women to behave themselves in an expected way and dictate what they should or should not do; how they should dress, behave, or present themselves in public and private. Role performance and expectations are basically all about the behaviors, roles, and responsibilities that men and women as intimate partners/spouses expect from each other. For example, gender roles are considered society's

communal beliefs which the society apply to individuals based on their socially identified sex. Gender role expectations are considered descriptive as well as prescriptive (Eagly, 2009; Eisenchlas, 2013). In most marriages, there is likelihood for couples to maintain a social constructed role performance and expectation as well as expect same from their partners which also disturb their psychological functioning (Koenig, 2018).

Stress generational model (Davila, et al., 1997) as a perspective that links marital quality and psychological well-being, posits that individuals with low psychological well-being engage in stressful interactions with their spouses whom unexpectedly they start viewing as an enemy, and in turn, these stressful interactions lead to even greater declines in psychological well-being. For example, a wife with low psychological wellbeing might withdraw from family life in hostility, creating tension and confrontations in her marital relationship and causing arguments with her husband. In turn, this tension might lead to further deterioration in the wife's well-being. Experiences at work, such as an overload of demands and negative social interactions, can also be a source of daily stress that affect couples social interactions as well as the individual's health and well-being (Repetti, et al., 2009; Repetti, et al., 2011). Research has typically conceptualized support as a coping resource that buffers the effects of stress on health and well-being (e.g. Taylor & Stanton, 2007), and studies examining economic pressure (Conger, et al., 1999), stress spill-over (Brock & Lawrence, 2008), and daily job stress have also supported this framework.

Emotional intelligence is another variable of concern and has also been linked to psychological well-being of married couples. The psychological concept known as emotional intelligence or emotional quotient is a phenomenon of the last quarter century, although has roots in much older social and psychological theories. According to Goleman, everybody has some level of emotional quotient and anyone can enhance their emotional intelligence to monitor their own emotions and emotional states. Mayer and Salovey (1997), regard emotional intelligence as a series of skills that combine cognition's (thoughts) and emotions (feelings). They define emotional intelligence in various ways such as the ability to recognize emotions, to access and use emotions to help support cognitive processes, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to handle or regulate emotions in order to promote emotional and intellectual development (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). Put in another way, emotional intelligence, according to these authors, is made up of four distinct components, identifying emotions (the ability to recognize emotions in the self and others); using emotions (the ability to invoke and reason with emotions); understanding emotions (the ability to understand complicated emotions and emotional states, especially how these emotions shift

from moment to moment); and managing emotions (controlling emotions in the self and others).

Contemporary studies have indicated that religiosity is a significant factor in preventing poor health, complaints, endorsement of wellness, and thriving adjustment to the everchanging circumstance of life (Pargament, 2005). This is an imperative contribution made by researchers within the psychology of religion, to study psychological well-being with religiosity. Previously a number of researchers argued on the subject whether religion has favorable or detrimental effects on the mental well-being of individuals (Crawford et al. 1989; Sharkey & Malony 1986). Religious orientation, beliefs, and practices are utilized as resources in order to tackle the difficulties of life. Christian and Islamic teachings guide people to have trust in God, be tolerant, to offer prayers, and turn to God in times of need. The teachings also provide people with noteworthy interpretations of difficulties in life. The Holy Bible and Quran evidently underscore that the hardships faced by people in the world are to test the believer as well as to make them learn enduring patterns to face the problems (Aflakseir 2012). Various research on religiosity and mental health shows a significant association between the variables (Amer et al. 2008; Hafeez & Rafique 2013).

In view of the above, this study aims to investigate the influence of stress, emotional intelligence and the religiosity on psychological well-being among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

There is considerable variability in married couple's experience which has led this study to examine the influence stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity on psychological well-being among married couples. Besides, a casual observation has shown that psychological well-being has been a major problem among married couples in Nigeria. The imbalance in couple's psychological well-being has become a current concern about married couples whose marriage has led to separation, divorce and even widowhood. Couples have drag themselves to court seeking divorce; some are found in psychiatric facilities because of discord in marriages and very often observe that religious leaders are counseling one family case or the other.

A survey in Nigeria uncovered the fact that marriages are becoming problematic and difficult to understand. Statistics from this survey shows that about 60% of marriages contracted within a year in Nigeria fail or are at the brink of failure (Adamu, 2010). According to Adamu (2010), the un-official failing or ailing marriages may probably be worse because

they are off record. Without doubt relations among couples are faced with several challenges (Ochigbo, 2015).

The psychological well-being of couples is a major pointer of a healthy family existence, as a result, there is a need to look at the mental, emotional, and behavioural factors that exert significant influences on the psychological well-being of couples with resultant influence on the quality of marital life. This study therefore seeks to bridge the gap in literature by finding the influence of stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity on psychological wellbeing of married couples in Makurdi Local Government.

Research Questions

The following research questions are stated in this study;

- i. What is the influence of stress on the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue state?
- ii. What is the influence of emotional intelligence on the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue state?
- iii. What is the influence of religiosity on the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?

Objectives of the study

The following are the objectives of this study

- i. Examine the significant influence of stress on psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.
- ii. Identify the significant influence of emotional intelligence on the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.
- iii. Explore significant influence of religiosity on the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria.
- iv. Assess the joint influence of stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity on psychological well-being among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study.

- i. There will be a significant influence of stress on the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria.

Emotional intelligence will significantly influence the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria.

- iii. There will be a significant influence of Religiosity on the psychological well-being of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria.
- iv. Stress, Emotional Intelligence and Religiosity will jointly influence the psychological wellbeing of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria.

Empirical Review of Literature

Stress and Psychological wellbeing

The prevalence of the unknown coronavirus disease as a stressful event, in addition to direct effects on health, due to forcing people to quarantine at home can have several psychological consequences on individuals. Limited studies in this area show that lockdown and being isolated have significantly increased feelings of loneliness, anxiety, stress, and suicide in people living in European and American countries (Brodeur et al., 2020). Other evidence suggests that children in quarantine situations experience feelings of anger, fear, loneliness, and boredom despite feeling happy and relaxed with family (Idoiaga, 2020). Conversely, the study of Recchi et al, (2020) on the French population before and after the outbreak of coronavirus indicated an improvement in well-being and health in the unaffected majority; however, people with low income and who lost their job or those who worked long hours at home reported higher levels of stress (Prickett et al, 2020)

Marital satisfaction as the indicator of the marriage quality (Fincham & Beach, 1999) is defined as the mental experience of happiness in a marital relationship (Hendrick et al., 1998), which reflects the perceived benefits and values of marriage (Baumeister & Vohs, 2007), a subjective evaluation that varies under the influence of happy and unpleasant life events (Li & Wickrama, 2014). The challenging events in the context of the family are changes, and people no longer simply feel satisfied after the changes (Maltas, 1992); changes caused by stressful events led to stress and act as a threat to satisfaction and intimate relationships (Randall & Bodenmann, 2009). Stressors, especially external factors, first by reducing opportunities to strengthen relationships and distracting couples from spending time to improve intimacy in relationships and then by weakening their abilities to cope with stressors, create problems for couples (Neff & Karney, 2017). Some studies have shown that external stressors including natural disasters are associated with decreased MS (Chi et al,

studies have also shown that stressful events (e.g. declining level of welfare and low income) have a significant association with decreasing marital stability (Bahr, 1979), poorer marital interactions and low MS, especially in the first years of marital life (Bodenmann, 2000; Bodenmann & Cina, 2006). sexual problems in intimate relationships (Bodenmann et al., 2007), criticism of spouse, and reduction of dyadic support (Neff & Karney, 2009), low MS, and high psychological distress with mediating role of problem-solving (Cohan & Bradbury, 1997) or management skills (Li & Wickrama, 2014) and coping strategies (Fink & Shapiro, 2013).

The prevalence of the COVID-19 pandemic as an external stress has challenged the quality of couples' relationships; home quarantine with negative psychological effects, such as anxiety, stress, depression, and frustration (Brodeur et al., 2020; Idoiaga Mondragon et al, 2020), and making changes in the unemployment rate and reducing access to financial opportunities (Coibion et al., 2020), forcing distress couples to spend many hours of the day together and increase the capacity for marital conflicts (Perez, 2020), can have negative effects on couples' relationships; these effects become more destructive due to different backgrounds, such as low economic quality and low levels of vulnerability (Pietromonaco & Overall, 2020). Kevin & Risla, (2020) showed that couples with low income reported low MS during the lockdown or distressed couples experience worse individual and dyadic outcomes in the face of external stress (Beach et al., 1994). Conversely, some other evidence suggests that external stresses in a good marital relationship, despite weakening the relationship at the beginning of the encounter to stress, cause spouses to adapt to new conditions and strengthen the dyadic relationship in later stages (Bonanno, 2004). Therefore, to clearly understand the effect of stress on couples' relationships, it is helpful to pay attention to the source of stress, the intensity of stress, and the duration of exposure to stress (Randall & Bodenmann, 2009) with regard to personal, relational, and cultural backgrounds of couples.

Emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing

Hollist and Miller (2005) found from their study on Perceptions of Attachment Style and Marital Quality in Midlife Marriage that insecure attachment styles were associated with marital quality, whereas secure attachment was not. This study was based on theoretical framework of Emotionally Focused Therapy (EFT); which theorizes that attachment styles influence marital quality. Hollist et al, (2005) examined this issue using data from 429 married people between the ages of 40 and 50. The authors concluded that, EFT therapists

can help midlife couples in distressed relationships move from insecure to secure attachment styles while still questioning the use of EFT to help couples who have secure attachment styles. In religion and marital satisfaction, several studies have examined the effects of religiosity on various outcomes related to marriage, such as marital satisfaction, marital conflict, divorce, marital stability and commitment, and cohabitation/marital outcomes among children of religious parents. Religiosity as measured by religious service attendance has been linked to higher levels of marital satisfaction, marital stability, less marital conflict, lower risk of divorce, and the probability of marriage among young adults (Call & Heaton, 1997). Other studies have found less clear relationships between religiosity and marital satisfaction (Sullivan, 2001; Booth, et al., 1995). Hunler et al; (2005) focused on revealing the effects of religiousness on marital satisfaction, and also to test the mediator role of perceived marital problem solving between religiousness and marital satisfaction relationship in a Turkish sample. Subjects were 92 married couples, or a total of 184 participants. Hierarchical regression analyses indicated that after controlling for the variance accounted for by the control variables, namely duration of marriage, marital style, educational level, hopelessness, and submissive acts; religiousness had a major effect on marital satisfaction, but a mediator role of problem solving was not observed.

Haseley (2006) also explored marital satisfaction among newly married couples: associations with religiosity and romantic attachment style with the purpose of examining the combined role of religious commitment and attachment in marital satisfaction. Heterosexual couples (N = 184; 92 husbands, 92 wives) without children and married 1-5 years were administered a background information questionnaire, the Religious Commitment Inventory-10, the Dyadic Adjustment Scale, and the Experiences in Close Relationships Inventory. Results indicated that couples with congruent religious commitment reported higher marital satisfaction than couples with large discrepancies in religious commitment. Religious commitment did not mediate the relationship between attachment and marital satisfaction, but instead was found to moderate this relationship. A study investigated the associations between parenting style and quality of child–mother attachment in middle childhood (n = 202; grades 4–6) and adolescence (n = 212; grades 7–11). Participants rated warm involvement, psychological autonomy granting, and behavioral monitoring (Steinberg, et al., 1994).

Taghizadeh and Kalhori, (2015) investigated the relationship between self-esteem and marital satisfaction in women employed in Payame Noor University of Shahre Rey in 2014. This is a descriptive-correlational study of cross-sectional type. Its population included 94 people.

Inclusion criteria were: Iranian nationality, married with at least one year of married life, etc. Results show that the majority of participants (55.6 %) had relative and moderate marital satisfaction. The majority of the samples (92 %) had high self-esteem. There was a significant relationship between marital satisfaction, economic status and sexual satisfaction. The results of the logistic regression analysis showed that probability of marital dissatisfaction in individual with low self-esteem is 9 times higher than normal people, 5 times among those with low sexual satisfaction, and 3 times among people dealing with bad economic condition. Results show that there is a significant relation between marital dissatisfaction and self-esteem, sexual satisfaction and economic status.

Sadia et al, (2014) explored the relationship between marital satisfaction and emotional intelligence among different professionals. The sample comprised of N= 200 participants (n= 100 men and n= 100 women). Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) by Schutte (1998) and Dyadic Adjustment Scale (DAS) by Spanier, (1976) were administered to measure the variables of emotional intelligence and marital satisfaction. The findings of the study indicated significant relationship between marital satisfaction and emotional intelligence. Results also supported that working women have higher emotional intelligence as compare to working men. Ahmad et al, (2014) investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence health and marital satisfaction among married people. Done on 226 people including 114 persons having marital conflicts, and 112 people having marital satisfaction, by cluster random sampling from 13 districts of the city of Isfahan, the correlation analysis showed that there was a significant and positive relation between emotional intelligence and marital satisfaction ($P < 0.001$, $r = 0.529$). The results of linear regression also showed that the general emotional intelligence predicts the quality of marital satisfaction among couples.

Religiosity and Psychological Wellbeing

Psychological well-being denotes positive mental health (Edwards, 2005). Literature reveals that the construct of psychological well-being is a multidimensional phenomenon (MacLeod & Moore 2000; Wissing & Van Eeden, 2002). It grows through a blend of emotional regulation, life experience, and personality traits (Helson & Srivastava 2001). Psychological well-being can enhance with age, education, extraversion, and consciousness, and decreases with neuroticism (Keyes et al., 2002). Research findings indicate a positive relationship between religiosity and mental health aspects, comprising of a faster recovery from depression, lower anxiety, lower rate of suicide, and reduction in drug abuse (Koenig 2004). Additionally, religiosity has also been connected with general psychological well-being,

including meaning in life, happiness, life satisfaction, hope and optimism, marital satisfaction, and social support (Koenig, 2001).

Research literature reveals that psychological well-being has a substantial relationship with spirituality and religiosity. In another study, the population (85 females and 65 males; age range =18–60 years) showed a positive relationship among religiosity and miscellaneous aspects of psychological well-being, whereas a negative relationship with solitude. In the study a linear regression analysis was conducted to discover the remarkable forecasters of psychological well-being. Among the independent variables, religiosity was found to be the imperative predictor of psychological well-being. The study also aimed at identifying gender differences in religiosity, spirituality and psychological well-being of old houses dwellers (Hafeez & Rafique 2013). Intrinsic orientation and psychological well-being are positively related, whereas extrinsic and quest orientations possess a negative relationship (Alandete & Valero 2013). Another research was done on Muslim students to investigate their understanding and views toward life and to determine the relationship between personal meaning, religiosity, and psychological well-being. An explicit relationship was observed between numerous parameters of personal meaning and various elements of spirituality, religiosity and psychological well-being (Aflakseir 2012). Recent years have observed a well-documented surge in interest in this area of research, and the available data provides contrasting outcomes that are hard to assimilate. The results of meta-reviews of quantitative studies indicate a positive correlation between religious conviction and psychological health. A bulk of research work measured diverse specific aspects of religiosity, e.g., church attendance, salience of beliefs. These effects have contributed to a budding accord about the prerequisite of multidimensional conceptualizations of religiosity. The religion aspects help in getting a deeper understanding any community. On the basis of the existing literature, it is worth investigating to have more facts in regard to religiosity and psychological well-being.

METHOD

This section deals with the methods, setting, participants, sampling, and instruments, procedure and data analysis, used in the study.

Research Design

This study employed the use of cross-sectional survey design. This is the type of design that collects data from the population at a point in time and the sample is regarded as a cross-

section of the population, thereby making it possible to explore the relationship between related variables and make inferences about the population of interest at that point in time (Fife-Schaw, 2000).

Participants

The target population for this study comprises 2,832 married couples, as recorded in the Makurdi Local Government Area population census of 2006. From the population, a sample size of 350 married individuals were selected for the study. A purposive sampling was employed in selecting the respondents. This technique was deemed appropriate due to the nature of the study, which required participants who met specific inclusion criteria such as legally married, residing in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State and married for at least one year. The sampling also considered couples who were available and willing to participate in the study during the period of data collection.

The study made use of “Taro Yamen’s formula” to determine the sample size from multinomial or heterogeneous population.

The formula is stated as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n=sample size required

N=population size

e=level of significance

1 and 2 are constant

Therefore, in applying the population of married couples, the sample size will

thus:

$$n = \frac{2,832}{1+2,832 (0.5)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2,832}{1+2,832 (0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{2,832}{1+7.08}$$

$$n = \frac{2,832}{8.08}$$

n = 350

Instruments

In order to collect data for the study, the researcher used four instruments, namely;

1. Stress Subtle of Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS)

The Stress Scale (adopted from DASS) by Lovibond and Lovibond (1993) was used in this study to measure the stress of married couples. The instrument consists of 14 items from the total of 42 items measuring negative emotional symptoms. Respondents are expected to rate the extent to which they have experienced each symptom over the past week on a 4-point severity/frequency scale ranging from: 0=Did not apply to me at all; 1=Applied to me to some degree, or some of the time; 2=Applied to me a considerable degree, or a good part of the time; to 3=Applied to me very much, or most of the time. Scores for the Stress scale are determined by summing the scores for the relevant 14 items. Internal consistencies (coefficient alpha) for each scale for the DASS normative sample as established by the authors were: Stress 0.90.

2. Emotional Intelligence Test (Palmer & Stough, 2001).

The 64-item self-report measure includes five dimensions – Emotional recognition and Expression, understanding Emotions External, Emotions Direct Cognition, Emotional Management and Emotional Control. The emotional intelligence test (is score on 5 point Likert scale, with 1 indicating never and 5 indicating Always. The test has internal reliability (Cronbach alpha) of .91 and subscale internal reliabilities between .75 and .86.3.

3. Religious Orientation Scale (ROS)

Religious orientation scale was developed by Allport and Ross (1967) to assess an individual's extrinsic/intrinsic religious orientation. It is a 20 items scale that represents possible opinions/ religious behaviours that an individual may have. The scale is measured on a 5 points Likert scale ranging from I strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree. It has a Cronbach alpha reliability co-efficient of .74

4. Psychological well-being (Ryff, 2007)

This scale was developed by psychologist Carol D. Ryff, (1989). The 42-item Psychological Wellbeing (PWB) Scale measures six aspects of wellbeing and happiness: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Married couples will ask to rate their own level of agreement based on the 6

...point Likert-style response from strongly disagree to strongly agree. (1 = strongly agree; 2 = some what agree; 3 = a little agree; 4 = neither agree or disagree; 5 = a little disagree; 6 = strongly disagree.). It has a Cronbach alpha reliability co-efficient of .89.

Procedure

Before administering the research instrument, the researcher followed a systematic procedure to ensure ethical compliance, respondent's readiness and the successful collection of reliable data. The researcher obtained permission from the relevant authorities in Makurdi Local Government Area to conduct the study in the community. Thereafter, the researcher visited selected wards and communities in Makurdi Local Government Area to meet with local leaders, religious heads and community representatives. The purpose of the study was explained to them in detail, and their cooperation was sought to facilitate access to potential respondents.

Trained research assistants familiar with local languages (e.g., Tiv and Idoma, Hausa) were recruited to assist in data administration. They were brief on the objective of the study, ethical considerations, and the administration of the questionnaire. Using the established sampling technique, households with eligible married couples were identified. Data collection was conducted over a period of four weeks, ensuring coverage across urban and rural area of Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State. Completed questionnaires were carefully collected, checked for completeness and securely stored for data entry and analysis.

Ethical considerations

- Informed consent was sought
- Approval were obtained from the necessary authorities and participants
- Research assistants were trained on the protocol of administrating psychological instruments.
- Participation was voluntary

RESULTS

This section presents results of the analysis that was performed from the data collected. The data were analyzed to test the hypotheses of this study and the results obtained are presented in tables and interpreted.

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 1: Inter-correlation among study variables

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	\bar{X}	SD
	-											89.7	12.5
Intrinsic religion	.079	-										34.1	6.9
Extrinsic religion	.141**	.232**	-									32.9	6.6
Emotional recognition	.822**	.242**	.276**	-								52.9	9.5
Understanding emotions	.878**	-.118**	.021	.566**	-							48.0	7.1
Direct recognition	.191**	.976**	.195**	.283**	.007	-						44.6	8.0
Emotional management	.051	.988**	.315**	.245**	-.167**	.954**	-					44.6	8.6
Emotional control	.498**	.215**	.780**	.661**	.444**	.219**	.243**	-				47.1	8.8
Emotional intelligence	.726**	.645**	.477**	.819**	.550**	.694**	.641**	.757**	-			57.2	8.2
Stress	.112**	.987**	.212**	.288**	-.100	.975**	.974**	.211**	.665**	-		46.1	9.7
Religiosity	.142**	.796**	.773**	.333**	-.059	.755**	.837**	.632**	.714**	.773**	67.1	10.7	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results presented in Table 1 revealed that there is no significant relationship between psychological well-being and intrinsic religious orientation ($r = .079$; $p > .05$), and emotional management ($r = .051$; $p < .01$). However, psychological well-being is significantly and positively related to extrinsic religious orientation ($r = .141$; $p < .01$), implying that couples who have high extrinsic religious orientation are more likely to have high better wellbeing. Similarly, correlational analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between psychological wellbeing and emotional recognition ($r = .822$; $p < .01$), implying been high on emotional recognition would consequentially results in improved psychological wellbeing. Additionally, there is a significant positive correlation between wellbeing and understanding emotions ($r = .878$; $p < .01$), implying that couples with high emotional understanding would have better wellbeing. Emotions direct recognition is significantly and positively related to psychological wellbeing ($r = .191$; $p < .01$), which means high direct emotions would among couples would results to better psychological wellbeing. Also, there is a significant and positive relationship between psychological wellbeing and emotional control ($r = .498$; $p < .01$), emotional intelligence ($r = .726$; $p < .01$), stress ($r = .112$; $p < .01$), and religiosity ($r = .142$; $p < .01$), indicating that increase in these variables results to a corresponding improvement in wellbeing among couples.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypotheses one stated that stress will significantly influence psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG. This hypothesis was tested using simple linear regressions and the results is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Simple regression analysis showing the influence of Stress on Psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG

Predictor Variables	R	R ²	df	F	β	t	Sig
Constant	.112	.013	1,329	4.168		23.815	.000
Stress					.112	2.042	.042

The result in Table 2 indicated that stress has a significant influence on psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG $R = .112$, $R^2 = .013$, $[F (1,329) = 4.168, P < .05]$, implying that stress has statistically significant influence on wellbeing. The result further indicated that stress accounts for 1.3% of the variance in psychological wellbeing among married couples. Based on this finding, hypothesis one was accepted.

Hypotheses two stated that emotional intelligence will significantly influence psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG. This hypothesis was tested using multiple linear regression and the results is presented in Table 3

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Table 3: Multiple regression analysis showing the influence of Emotional Intelligence on Psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG

Predictor Variables	R	R ²	df	F	β	t	Sig
Constant	.973	.946	5,321	1111.736		5.594	.000
Emotional recognition					.567	7.157	.000
Understanding emotional					.656	14.003	.000
Emotions direct					.119	1.002	.317
Emotions control					-.135	-1.734	.084
Emotional management					-.080	-.352	.725

The result in Table 3 indicated that emotional intelligence has significant influence on psychological wellbeing among married couples $R = .973$, $R^2 = .946$, $[F (5,321) = 1111.736, P < .01]$. Furthermore, the result shows that emotional intelligence accounts for 94.6% of the variance in psychological wellbeing among married couples. Independently, emotional recognition ($\beta = .567, t = 7.157, p < .01$) and emotional understanding ($\beta = .656, t = 14.003, p < .01$) made significant positive contribution to the model, implying that couples who have emotional recognition and emotional understanding are likely to experience better psychological wellbeing, while emotions direct ($\beta = .119, t = 1.002, p > .05$), emotions control ($\beta = -.135, t = -1.734, p > .05$) and emotional management ($\beta = -.080, t = -.352, p > .05$) did not have significant relationship with psychological wellbeing. Based on this finding, hypothesis one was accepted.

Hypotheses three stated that religiosity will significantly influence wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG. This hypothesis was tested using multiple linear regression and the results is presented in Table 4

Table 4: Multiple regression analysis showing the influence of Religiosity on Psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG

Predictor Variables	R	R ²	df	F	β	t	Sig
Constant	.151	.023	2,345	3.989		18.379	.000
Intrinsic religion					.053	.960	.338
Extrinsic religion					.130	2.361	.019

The result in Table 4 revealed that religiosity has significant influence on psychological wellbeing among married couples $R = .151, R^2 = .023, [F (2,345) = 3.989, P < .01]$.

Furthermore, the result shows that religiosity accounts for 2.3% of the variance in psychological wellbeing among married couples. Independently, intrinsic religious orientation ($\beta = .053, t = .960, p > .05$) did not make significant contribution to the model, and extrinsic religious orientation ($\beta = .130, t = 2.361, p < .05$) made significant positive contribution to the model. Based on this finding, hypothesis three was accepted.

Hypotheses four stated that stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity will significantly and jointly influence psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG. This hypothesis was tested using multiple linear regression and the results is presented in Table 5

Table 5: Multiple regression analysis showing the joint influence of stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity on Psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi LG

Predictor Variables	R	R ²	df	F	β	t	Sig
Constant	.915	.937	3,321	542.750		8.160	.000
Stress					-.533	-13.687	.000
Emotional intelligence					1.333	39.732	.000
Religiosity					-.341	-9.323	.000

The result in Table 5 shows that stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity have significantly and jointly influenced psychological wellbeing among married couples $R = .915, R^2 = .937, [F (3,321) = 542.750, P < .01]$. Furthermore, the result shows that stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity accounts for 93.7% of the variance in psychological wellbeing among married couples. Based on this finding, hypothesis three was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

This study aims to investigate the influence of stress, emotional intelligence and the religiosity on the psychological wellbeing of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State. While, hypothesis one which stated that stress will significantly influence psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council was found to be significant. This means that, the more couples experience stress in their marriage, the higher their scores on measure of measures of psychological wellbeing. This finding is consistent with the study of Recchi et al, (2020) who found that partners' stress from daily hassles may not only reduce couples' relationship satisfaction in a direct way but also indirectly through two main mediating mechanisms: increase in stress (relationship stress)

and deterioration of individual psychological and physical well-being. Couples who experience stress may tend to spend less time together as a couple, reducing their sense of togetherness and intimacy.

Problematic personal characteristics such as hostility, intolerance, or rigidity may be exacerbated and manifest more prominently, which may contribute to negative interactions. In addition, due to their seemingly triviality, daily stresses may not be accompanied by a partner's support or empathic understanding as major life stressors often are. This emotional distance and conflict that daily stresses may bring to the marital relationship can create additional sources of stress for each partner, which in turn may contribute to feeling less of psychological wellbeing or satisfied with the couple's relationship. The current study is also in line with two previous studies which provided empirical support for the role of stress in the reduced psychological wellbeing and relationship satisfaction (Bodenmann, et al., 2007; Brodeur et al., 2020).

The second Hypothesis which emotional intelligence has significant influence on psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council was also found to be significant. In other words, the result indicated that emotional intelligence accounts for 94.6% of the variance in psychological wellbeing among married couples. Independently, emotional recognition and emotional understanding made significant positive contributions to the model, implying that couples who have emotional recognition and emotional understanding are likely to experience better psychological wellbeing, while emotions direct, emotions control and emotional management did not have significant relationship with psychological wellbeing. This finding is in line previous study by Haseley (2006) who found support for the positive association between emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing components such as self-esteem, life satisfaction, and self-acceptance. Similarly, Taghizadeh and Kalhori, (2015) also found a result that suggested that romantic partners' self-rated EI impacts some aspects of psychological wellbeing.

Emotionally intelligent couple tends to have higher psychological wellbeing. It is possible that their high emotional intelligence (EI) also affects the psychological wellbeing of their spouses they interact with. This is particularly true in romantic relationships, where a person's EI may play an important role in their partner's emotional experiences (Sadia et al, 2014).

The third hypothesis which stated that religiosity will significantly and independently predict psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Council was found to be significant. That is to say that religiosity significantly and positively predicted psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Council. This implies that Makurdi Local Council who scored high on measure of religiosity appeared to score high on measure of psychological wellbeing. The findings is consistent with the finding of (MacLeod & Moore 2000; Wissing & Van Eeden, 2002) found that older women in highly religious, homogamous marriages report better psychological wellbeing (mental and physical health) relative to women in heterogamous and secular (non-religious) marriages. Their results emphasized that religiosity is an individual trait that have important implications for older couple's psychological well-being.

Religiosity could have a positive impact on the psychological well-being of couples. Studies suggest that shared religious beliefs and practices can enhance marital satisfaction, reduce conflict, and foster a stronger sense of commitment. Religiosity can also provide a framework for coping with stress, offering support and a sense of purpose, ultimately contributing to overall psychological well-being of married people (Alandete & Valero 2013; WHO, 2020; Hafeez & Rafique 2013). Shared religious beliefs and practices can strengthen the marital bond and lead to greater satisfaction within the relationship (WHO, 2020). Religious values can increase commitment to the relationship, potentially reducing the likelihood of divorce (Hafeez & Rafique 2013). Overall, research suggests that religiosity, when practiced in a healthy and balanced way can be a positive influence on the psychological well-being of couples by promoting marital satisfaction, reducing conflict, and providing a framework for coping with life's challenges.

The fourth hypothesis which stated that stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity will significantly and jointly influence psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council was found to be significant. Furthermore, the result shows that stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity accounts for 93.7% of the variance in wellbeing among married couples. This implies that stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity significantly and jointly predicted psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity on psychological wellbeing of married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council of Benue State. The study concluded as follows:

1. That stress influenced psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council.
2. That emotional intelligence influenced psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council.
3. That religiosity influenced psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council
4. That stress, emotional intelligence and religiosity jointly influenced influences psychological wellbeing among married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council

Recommendations

Based on the outcomes of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Interventions aiming to reduce stress levels and to enhance psychological wellbeing can be offered to the married couples in Makurdi Local Government Council. Examples of stress management interventions include stress inoculation training, physical activity, progressive muscle relaxation, guided imagery relaxation, and mindfulness-based intervention.
2. Emotional intelligence is a learned skill that should be developed by every couple in order to succeed in both life and marital relationship. Psychological well-being can be improved by emotional intelligence because people with greater emotional intelligence are able to understand their own emotions as well as others' emotions, and eventually able to link with them. By this way, various problems that possibly arise due to low emotional intelligence such as anxiety, stress and conflict can be avoided in marriage.
3. Clinical psychologists, couple or marriage therapist and Social Service agencies can consider incorporating religiosity into interventions to improve couple's psychological well-being.

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